

Original Research Report

Complementary Dietary Practices for Infants among Educated and Non-Educated Women

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Abstract: This study examined the complementary dietary practices for infants among educated and non-educated women of Ife central local government area of Osun State, Nigeria. It was a descriptive survey research. A total of one hundred and fifty (154) respondents participated in this research. The research instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire on a 4-point scale. The major findings of the study revealed the complementary dietary practices for infants, identified possible factors affecting complementary dietary practice which are economic status, maternal education, employment status, residence type. It further revealed effects of inadequate complementary dietary practices which include sub-optimal growth and development and malnutrition, low intelligence level and others and revealed possible strategies to be adopted for adequate and proper complementary feeding practices which are provision of accurate dietary information to care givers and family at large, introduction of developmental health system. Based on the findings, recommendations were made among which are adequate information should be given to upcoming mothers, hospitals, clinic and health center officials should educate mothers about the appropriate time to start feeding their children on complementary diet, mothers should breastfeed for at least six months of age before introducing semi-solid food to their children.

Keywords: Breastfeeding, Complementary, Dietary practices, Growth, Health

1. Introduction

Globally, appropriate infants and young children feeding comprising of breastfeeding and complimentary feeding practices plays an essential role in child growth, development and survival. Complementary feeding is defined as the process starting when breast milk alone is not sufficient to meet the nutritional requirement of infants and therefore other foods and liquids are needed along with breast milk. It is also the process of introducing other foods which are non-breast milk or nutritive liquids to young children from age 6 to 24 months (World Health Organization, WHO, 2017). It is a transition from exclusive breastfeeding to family food and venerable period in which malnutrition starts in many infants contributing significantly to the high prevalence of malnutrition in children less than 5 years of age worldwide. Inappropriate complimentary diet practices during the first two years of childhood drastically increase mobility, risk of chronic disease. Poor complimentary diet practices have detrimental effect on overall growth and development of a child (Black et al., 2013; Joseph et al., 2011). Mothers are responsible for feeding their children concurrently and to ensure adequate eating practices of their children, poor nutritional status of children reflects their imbalance in dietary intake and it is affected by multiple, environmental and socioeconomic factor such as low income family (Hien & His, 2019; Phuka et al., 2009)

Education is the best legacy a nation can give to their citizen especially the mothers because training a woman implies training a nation. Education is the process of transmitting what is worldwide to members of the society, it is the process of socializing the citizen to a grown up, as a fulfilled member of the society through informal, formal, and non-formal process. Among the entire factor influencing adequate complementary feeding practices, mother education has greater impact on the nutritional status of children. Education system in any society reflects and adapts itself to the political and economic circumstances of the society. This is proven by a study done by (Carleti et al., 2017) in which it was stated that low education of mother's results in various degrees of malnutrition. However, it does not mean that only mother with high education has healthy children (Arikpo et al., 2018). A mother with high level of education usually starts complimentary food at appropriate time for her infants because of her knowledge on the correct timing of compliments diet practices compared to those with low level of education. Mothers are the main care giver of their children and have stronger effect on the child growth rate compares to the fathers (Steyn et al., 2006).

Stunting is associated with maternal education, thus in order to overcome the prevalence of malnutrition among children, mothers need to improve their education, boost human health status and create healthy environment (Costa, 2016). Mother's education level can influence the dietary practice, thus, this research is done to study the complimentary diet practices for infants among educated and non-educated women. We believe that the adequacy of complementary diet practice is determined by the combined effect of the socio-economic and cultural factors, household and caregiver characteristics in association with factors related to mother's education level. Therefore, this research examines the complimentary dietary practices among educated and non-educated women in Ife central local government in Osun State, Nigeria.

1.1. Statement of Problem

Malnutrition is undesirable and may be as a result of inadequate or excessive intake of essential nutrient in the diet which may result in ill-health. Therefore, inappropriate complementary diet affects a child's growth, development and dramatically increases mobility and mortality and risk

of chronic disease. It also influences the most mental ability and response in the society, inappropriate complimentary diet can lead to death of an infant. In 2015, approximately 6 million deaths under five years old were reported in Nigeria and more than 67 percent of deaths were attributed to inappropriate child's diet practice. Evidence has equally shown that promotion of appropriate and adequate complementary feeding practices reduces the incidence of stunting, ill-health, and morbidity. It leads to better and growth. It is therefore pertinent to investigate the complementary practices among mothers and its relationship to their level of education in Ife Central Local government, Osun State and suggest possible way of eradicating its menace.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this research is to examine the complimentary dietary practices among educated and non-educated women in Ife central local government in Osun State. Specific purpose is to:

- (a) Assess the complementary dietary practices for infants among educated and non-educated woman in Ife Central Local Government Area of Osun State.
- (b) Identify the factors affecting complementary dietary practices for infants among educated and non-educated women in Ife Central Local Government Area of Osun State.
- (c) Highlight the effect of inadequate complementary dietary practices for infants among educated and non-educated women in Ife Central Local Government Area of Osun State.
- (d) Suggest possible strategies that could be adopted for adequate and proper complementary dietary practices for infants among educated and non-educated women in Ife Central Local Government Area of Osun State.

1.3. Research Questions

The following research question guided the study:

- (a) What are the complimentary dietary practices in Ife Central Local of Osun State?
- (b) What are the factors affecting complimentary dietary practices in Ife Central Local Government Area of Osun State?
- (c) What are the effects of inadequate complimentary dietary in Ife Central Local Government Area of Osun State?
- (d) What are the possible strategies that would be adopted for adequate and proper complimentary feeding practices in Ife Central Local Government Area of Osun State?

2. Materials and Methods

1.1. Design for the Study

The descriptive survey research design was used for this study. To achieve this, the survey method was adopted and the quantitative data were generated using the questionnaire. The use of this research design is considered appropriate because of its merit, which suit a study of this nature. Banke-Thomas, et al. (2016) concur that descriptive research design helps a researcher in the collection of information, identifying problems, making comparison and carrying out systematic evaluation.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

The study was approved by the Faculty Research Ethics Review Committee and the authors sought out informed oral consent of the respondents. The researchers also complied with other

ethical requirements for human subject research including anonymity and confidentiality of respondents' information.

2.2. Area of the Study

This study was carried out in Ife Central Local Government of Osun state. Ife Central Local Government is one of the thirty (30) Local Governments Areas in Osun state. It has an area in the city of Ile-IFE to the South of the Area of 111km² and a population of 167,254 (National population commission, 2006). It has eleven (11) areas namely Iremo, Ilare, Moore, Ojaja, Opa, Abacoker, Okerewe, Ajebandele, Eleyele, Akarabata, Ilode. The indigenes are mostly farmers.

2.3. Population and Sample

The population of this study consisted of all women in Ife Central Local Government, Ile Ife Osun state. Purposive sampling was used to select educated and non-educated women that constituted the respondents. This sampling technique is used first because the respondents are selected deliberately to be women who can provide in-depth and detailed information about the phenomenon under investigation. Also, it is cost and time effective. Fourteen respondents were selected randomly from each of the eleven (11) wards in Ife Central Local Government, Ile Ife Osun state giving a total of one hundred and fifty-four (154) respondents.

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure

A questionnaire, titled "complimentary dietary practices for infants among educated and non-educated women in ife central local government in osun state" was used as the main instrument of data collection. The questions were structured to answer the research questions for this study. The questionnaire was drafted by the researchers and it consisted of five (5) sections (A, B, C, D, E and F). Section A consisted of the respondents' personal data while, sections B, C, D, E and F were drawn to obtain information on the four (4) research questions raised in this study. The total number of items on the questionnaire is fifty (35). The questionnaire adopted the four Likert scales of Strongly Agree (SA, 4 points), Agree (A, 3 points), Disagree (D, 2 points) and Strongly Disagree (SD, 1 point). This is to allow the researchers to easily operationalize personality traits or perceptions. It was validated by three experts in food and nutrition in Department of Home Economics, Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo. The reliability index was estimated using Spearman Ranking Order Correlation and the value was 0.84. one hundred and fifty-four (154) of the questionnaire were produced and administered by the researchers with the help of two trained research assistant. The language of instruction was English language and the filled copies of the questionnaire were collected back immediately to avoid loss in transit.

2.5. Data Collection Technique

The questionnaire was administered personally by the researcher with the aid of two research assistants who have been trained on how to collect data. One hundred and fifty-four (154) copies of the questionnaire were produced and administered to the respondents and were collected immediately to avoid loss in transits.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

The responses to the questionnaire items were collected and analyzed using mean and standard deviation. The mean of the questionnaire items were used and interpreted based on the statistics real limit of the number as follows: strongly Agree (SA)=4, Agree (A)=3, Disagreed (D)=2, Strongly Disagree (SD)=1. A cut off point was used to determine the accepted and rejected items. The cutoff point (C.O.P) was obtained by totaling the nominal value divided by the number of nominal value. That is, $C.O.P = \frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = \frac{10}{4} = 2.5$. Any mean of 2.50 and above were regarded as

agreed, while any mean below 2.50 were considered as disagreed.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of responses of the respondents on complimentary dietary practices in Ife Central Local of Osun State

N ₁ =154, N ₂ =77, N ₃ =77, COP=2.5						
S/N	Items	\bar{x}_1	SD	\bar{x}_2	\bar{x}_3	Decision
1a	Practice of exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months of age	2.99	0.993	2.65	2.52	Agreed
1b	Continue breastfeeding	2.71	1.102	2.81	2.79	Agreed
2a	Feed slowly and patiently	2.47	1.178	2.56	2.71	Disagreed
2b	Do not force feed rather encourage them	3.23	.839	2.19	2.81	Agreed
2c	Minimize distractions during feeding	3.37	0.741	2.78	2.83	Agreed
3a	Washing of caregivers and children's hand before food preparation and eating	2.71	0.921	2.64	2.69	Agreed
3b	Storing foods safely and serving food immediately after preparation	3.08	1.129	2.64	2.52	Agreed
3c	using clean equipment and bowls when feeding is essential	3.08	1.007	2.61	2.79	Agreed
4a	Increasing the number of times children are fed as one get older	2.80	1.122	2.62	2.71	Agreed
4b	Food should be provided Five times per day at 9-11 and 12-24 months	2.78	1.133	2.66	2.81	Agreed
4c	Additional nutritious snacks such as (fruits, nuts) offered once or twice per day	2.34	1.055	2.66	2.83	Disagreed
5a	Proteinous food such as Fish, egg should be eaten daily	2.96	0.976	2.68	2.69	Agreed
5b	Fruits and vegetable rich in vitamin A should be eaten daily or incorporated infants food	2.76	0.984	2.66	2.52	Agreed
5c	Avoid giving drinks with low nutrient value such as tea, coffee, sugary drinks	2.64	1.187	2.66	2.77	Agreed
5d	Use of vitamin-mineral supplements fortified products for infant and mother	2.72	1.117	2.70	2.65	Agreed

Key: \bar{x}_1 = Total mean response of the respondents, \bar{x}_2 = mean response of the educated respondents, \bar{x}_3 =mean response of the non-educated respondents, N₁= Total numbers of respondents, COP= cut

off point, SD= standard deviation, N_2 = number of educated respondents, N_3 =number of Non-educated respondents

Table 1 revealed that the mean responses of item 1a, 1b, 2b, 2c, 3a, 3b, 3c, 4a, 4b, 4c, 5a, 5b, 5c, and 5d ranged from 2.64 to 3.37 which were greater than the cut-off point (2.50). This implies that respondents agreed with all the items as complimentary dietary practices. However, the mean responses on 2a and 4c were below the cut- off point (2.50), which means that the respondents did not agree with the items as part of the complementary dietary practices. The standard deviation ranged from 0.741-1.187 and were low this indicates that the responses were clustered around the mean. This research discovered exclusive breastfeeding practices for the first six months of age, continued breastfeeding to 2 years, feeding slowly and patiently, not force feeding, minimizing distraction during feeding, washing of children and caregivers hands before or after feeding, storing food safely and serving food immediately after preparation, using clean equipment's and bowls is essential, increasing the number of times children are fed as they get older, food should be provided five times per day, additional nutritious snacks should be provided per day, proteinous food such as fish, egg should be eaten daily, fruit and vegetables rich in vitamin A should be eaten daily or incorporated in infants food, avoid giving drinks with low nutrients value such as tea, coffee, and sugary drinks, imbibing the use of supplement of vitamin and mineral products for infants and their mothers are the complementary dietary practices for infants in Ife central local government area of Osun state (Nasrul et al., 2020).

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of responses of the respondents on factors affecting complimentary practices in Ife Central Local Government of Osun state?

$N_1=154, N_2=77, N_3=77, COP=2.5$

S/N	Items	\bar{x}_1	SD	\bar{x}_2	\bar{x}_3	Decision
1	Parental economic status influence adequate complementary diet practices for infants	2.73	1.195	2.88	2.65	Agreed
2	Environment has significance influence on infant food choice	2.60	1.228	2.99	2.95	Agreed
3	Accessibility to food affects complementary practices for infants	2.72	1.135	2.47	2.56	Agreed
4	Breastfeeding mothers who attend post natal clinic are well informed about infant complementary diets	2.74	1.170	2.61	2.19	Agreed
5	Underage mothers practice adequate complementary diet	2.71	1.131	2.61	2.52	Agreed
6	Duration of breast feeding has strong influence on child's health	2.76	1.177	2.58	2.53	Agreed
7	Mothers with high level of education have more awareness about feeding practices of children	2.86	1.123	2.88	2.56	Agreed
8	Maternal employment influence child feeding practice	2.55	1.155	2.71	2.73	Agreed
9	The size of the family determines complementary diets practices for infants	2.79	1.154	2.82	2.56	Agreed

Key: \bar{x}_1 = Total mean response of the respondents, \bar{x}_2 = mean response of the educated

respondents, \bar{x}_3 =mean response of the non-educated respondents, N_1 = Total numbers of respondents, COP= cut off point, SD= standard deviation, N_2 = number of educated respondents, N_3 =number of Non-educated respondents

The findings in Table 2 revealed that the mean responses of item 1 to 9 ranged from 2.55 to 2.86 which were greater than the cut-off point (2.50). Thus, respondents agreed with all items as factors affecting complimentary practices in Ife Central Local Government of Osun state. The standard deviation ranged from 1.123 - 1.195; this indicates that the responses were clustered around the mean. WHO Multicentre Growth Reference Study Group (2006) supported that complimentary diet is needed from that age size milk or breast formula feeding alone is not sufficient. The study also revealed that parental economy status, complementary diet practices for infants: significant dietary influence the infants breastfeeding mothers who attend postnatal clinic are well-informed about the infant complementary diet; underage mother's practice: adequate complementary diet; duration of breastfeeding influence child's health; mothers with high-level of education have more awareness about feeding practices of children; maternal employment influence child feeding practices and the size of the family determines complementary dietary practices for infants. Nasrul et al., (2020) reported several factors known to be associated with exclusive breastfeeding and a complimentary diet for infants' practices that includes economic status of a parents, maternal education, and residence type.

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of responses of the respondents on possible effect of inadequate complementary diet practices

$N_1=154, N_2=77, N_3=77, COP=2.5$

S/N	Items	\bar{x}_1	SD	\bar{x}_2	\bar{x}_3	Decision
1	Complementary diet have detrimental effect on the overall growth and development of a child	2.86	1.123	2.73	2.57	Agreed
2	Inadequate complementary diet practices could result in child illness, sub-optimal growth and development	2.65	1.155	2.39	2.74	Agreed
3	Unsuitable complementary diet practices affect child's cognitive and psychomotor development	2.79	1.154	2.65	2.68	Agreed
4	Pneumonia caused by poor complementary diet for infants	2.88	1.151	2.75	2.70	Agreed
5	Inappropriate complementary diet practice affect child's intelligent level	2.82	1.146	2.66	2.73	Agreed
6	Malaria as a result of poor complementary diet practices	2.90	1.074	2.78	2.64	Agreed
7	Poor complementary diet result	2.86	1.123	2.73	2.84	Agreed

can result in malnutrition

Key: \bar{x}_1 = Total mean response of the respondents, \bar{x}_2 = mean response of the educated respondents, \bar{x}_3 =mean response of the non-educated respondents, N_1 = Total numbers of respondents, COP= cut off point, SD= standard deviation, N_2 = number of educated respondents, N_3 =number of Non-educated respondents

Table 3 revealed that the mean responses of item 1 to 6 ranged from 2.65 to 2.90 which were greater than the cut-off point (2.50). Therefore, respondents agreed with all the item possible effect of inadequate complementary diet practices. The standard deviation ranged from 1.074 – 1.155 and were low, this indicates that the responses were clustered around the mean. Complementary diet has detrimental effects on the overall growth and development of a child; inadequate complementary dietary practice could result in child illness, suboptimal growth; unsuitable complimentary diets practice affects the child cognitive and psychomotor development; pneumonia caused by poor complementary diet for infants; in appropriate complementary dietary practices effects child's intelligence level; malaria as a result of poor complementary diet practice and poor complementary diet results in malnutrition. Brown et al. (2014) estimated that appropriate complementary diet practice contribute to 17% reduction in the prevalence stunting at 24 months of age and could avert suboptimal feeding practices and infectious disease – the main immediate causes of undernutrition for the first two years of life. WHO (2017) also recommended for infants to be exclusively breastfed for six months of life and to be adequately, safely and appropriately fed complementary food from 6 to 24 months in order to meet the evolving needs of the growing infant. Inappropriate complementary practice for the first two years of infants dramatically increases morbidity, mortality and risks of chronic diseases. Poor complementary diet practices have detrimental effect on the overall growth of a child (Black et al., 1982). October (2011) reported that inappropriate complementary diet practice could result in child illness, suboptimal growth and development. The period of birth to two years of age is a critical window for promotion of optimal growth and development which are directly dependent on nutrition. Huang et al. (2020) also emphasize that an appropriate diet is a critical component for growth and development of a child.

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation of responses of the respondents on possible strategies to be adopted for adequate and proper complementary feeding practices

$N_1=154, N_2=77, N_3=77, COP=2.5$

S/N	Items	\bar{x}_1	SD	\bar{x}_2	\bar{x}_3	Decision
1	Provision of accurate information to family, community and new development from health system	2.76	0.997	2.79	2.56	Agreed
2	Government should provide community based technology to ensure nutrients dense, bioavailability and the micro nutrients content of local foods	3.04	0.969	2.78	2.56	Agreed
3	Sound and culturally-appropriate counselling should be given to mothers of young children on how they can make widest possible use of indigenous	2.66	1.025	2.64	2.70	Agreed

	locally available foods					
4	The agricultural sector should ensure that suitable foods for use in complementary feeding are produced, readily available and affordable	2.88	1.060	2.67	2.83	Agreed

Key: \bar{x}_1 = Total mean response of the respondents, \bar{x}_2 = mean response of the educated respondents, \bar{x}_3 =mean response of the non-educated respondents, N_1 = Total numbers of respondents, COP= cut off point, SD= standard deviation, N_2 = number of educated respondents, N_3 =number of Non-educated respondents

The findings of the study suggested that there should be provision of accurate information to caregivers and family and community, government should provide community-based technology to ensure bioavailability and micronutrients contents of local foods; sound and culturally-appropriate counselling should be given to mothers of young children on how they make widest possible use of indigenous local available food, and the agricultural sector should ensure suitable food for use in the complementary feeding which are produced readily available and affordable. In line with this, WHO (2017) had stressed that the optimal feeding depends on the accurate information and skilled support from the family community and the health system. Inadequate knowledge about appropriate food and feeding practices is often a greater determinant of malnutrition than lack of food. Provision of adequate information about local food plays a vital role in introducing complementary dietary feeding for infants. Senerath et al. (2007) is in support of this assertion, with the view that the agricultural sector has an important role to play in ensuring that suitable foods for use in complementary feeding are produced, readily available and affordable.

Ajani (2016) equally supported that continue breastfeeding after two years of age is an important source of energy, protein and micronutrients providing 35 to 40% of energy needed; it is also a good source of fat, vitamin calcium and riboflavin. Continuing breastfeeding along with complimentary food during this period results in decreased risk of morbidity and mortality especially in populations with high risk of contamination. It was suggested by Golden (2019) for mothers to feed infants directly and be sensitive to their hunger and encourage them to eat and not force-feed them. He also said feeding time should incorporate eye-to-eye contact by loving moments of learning and body contact with the child. WHO (2018) reported that complementary food should be safely prepared and stored since food hygiene and proper food handling practices minimize contamination. WHO Multicentre Growth Reference Study Group (2006) also suggested that the amount of food should be adequate for child's age. Introducing small amount of food at 6 months and increasing the quantity as a child gets older while maintaining frequent breastfeeding is in line with the reports of Hoffman et al. (2014). Mothers should gradually increase food constitutes and varieties as infant gets older and adapting to the infants requirements and ability. Infant can get pureed, mashed and semi-solid food at the beginning and 6 months, and by 8 months, most infants can also eat finger food, snacks that can be eaten by children.

The study outcomes therefore imply that the practice of appropriate complementary diet plays an essential role in a child's growth and development because, if otherwise, it could bring about malnutrition, increase morbidity and risk of chronic diseases. In the light of the above, mothers being the caregivers that are responsible for feeding their children must be given sound, cultural and appropriate nutritional education programs that will enlighten them about safe, adequate and appropriate complimentary dietary practices irrespective of their level of education. The study is

limited to complimentary dietary practices for infants among educated and non-educated women in Ife central local government area of Osun State. Further studies should be carried out in other local government areas of Osun State and the nation at large.

4. Conclusion

Complementary diet plays an essential role in a child growth and development and it is a very crucial step to take in order to aid children's growth and survival. Inappropriate complementary diet practices during the first two year of childhood dramatically increase morbidity and risk of chronic diseases. Mothers are responsible for feeding their child concurrently hence, it was concluded that Sound, cultural and appropriate nutritional education should be given to both educated and non-educated mothers. In the light of the above, adequate information and orientation should be given to women before and after birth on the importance and constituents of adequate and appropriate complementary diet. Social media should be used to make available education programs that will enlighten mothers about safe, adequate and appropriate complimentary dietary practices and mothers should follow guidelines for safe introduction of complementary diets to their infants. Mothers should breastfeed for at least 6 months of age before introducing semi-solid food to their child.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

The authors confirm contribution to the paper as follows: study conception and design: Adijat Ayodeji Adisa, Monsurat Bello; data collection: Adijat Ayodeji Adisa; Adijat Ayodeji Adisa, Monsurat Bello, Cecilia A. Olarewaju; draft manuscript preparation: Monsurat Bello, Cecilia A. Olarewaju. All authors reviewed the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Data Availability Statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article. Further enquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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